

Chemical Investigation of *Daphne cannabina* Wall (Fam. Thymelaceae)

P. L. Majumder and G. C. Sengupta

*Daphne cannabina*¹ (Beng. Syn: *Paharisone*) is a small tree abundantly available from Chamibu to Bhutan and in the middle hill-forests of Darjeeling. The stem-bark possesses a characteristic irritating smell. The internal appliance of the roots of the plant causes diarrhoea and vomiting tendencies which are known² to clean out poison from an affected person. The leaves of the plant have recently been reported^{3,4} to contain taraxerol, taraxerol acetate and taraxerone. We now report the isolation of two compounds, Compound A and Compound B from the stem-bark and root-bark of the plant.

Compound A has molecular formula C₁₉H₁₂O₇ (M⁺ 352), m.p. 244-45° (<)_D ± 0° (CHCl₃). It gave positive tests for coumarin and exhibited absorption maxima in the ultraviolet region λ_{max}^{EtOH} 232, 267, 325 and 343 mμ and λ_{sh}^{EtOH} 302 and 360 mμ characteristic of coumarin compounds.^{5,6,7}

The infrared spectrum indicated the presence of hydroxyl function (3380 cm⁻¹), an intense carbonyl band for <β-unsaturated six membered-lactone (1720 cm⁻¹) and an ether-linkage (1290 cm⁻¹) in the compound. It formed an acetate, m.p. 233°.

Dephnoretin

1. Index Seminum, 1965, Quae Hortus Botanicus, Darjeelinsis Promutua Commutatione, Lloyds Botanic Garden, Darjeeling.
2. K. Biswas, "Common Medicinal Plants of Darjeeling and the Sikkim Himalayas".
3. P. C. Maiti, A. K. Barua, A. K. Ray and S. Ray, *Science & Culture*, 1963, 29, 160.
4. P. C. Maiti, *Curr. Sci.*, 1957, **99**, (no. 4).
5. R. Tschesche, U. Scott, G. Legler, *Annalen*, 1963, **662**, 116.
6. A. Robertson and T. S. Subramaniam, *Jour. Chem. Soc.*, (Lond.), 1937, and *Jour. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **81**, 6331.
7. J. N. Chatterjee and N. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 39-41.

From the above observations, the compound appeared to be daphnoretin⁸ (7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-3-7'-dicumaryl ether).

Finally the identity of the compound was established by comparison (m.m.p., TLC and superimposable IR) with an authentic sample of daphnoretin, kindly supplied by Professor Rudolf Tschesche, University of Bonn, West Germany.

Compound B has the molecular formula, $C_{29}H_{50}O$, m.p. 135-37°, $(\alpha)_D = -35^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). It developed a green colouration for sterol with Liebermann-Burchardt reagent. It formed an acetate, m.p. 128-30°. The compound was found to be identical (m.m.p. and T.L.C.) with authentic β -sitosterol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of Daphnoretin: The powdered bark of the stem and the root (1 kg) of *Daphne cannabina* was Soxhletted for 72 hr. with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and the defatted material was extracted for another 72 hr. with chloroform.

The chloroform extract was concentrated (25 ml) and cooled overnight in a refrigerator. A yellowish brown crystalline mass (A) deposited (3 gms). It was filtered off. The mother liquor was first chromatographed on silica gel (200 g). The benzene-chloroform (1:1) eluate on concentration gave crystalline solid, m.p. 240° (yield 0.015%). It was recrystallised from methanol in colourless fine needles, m.p. 244-45° (yield 0.01%), $(\alpha)_D \pm 0^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). The compound was found to be homogeneous by TLC, using silica gel as adsorbent, ethylacetate-ethanol in the ratio of 3:1 ($R_f=0.58$) and chloroform-methanol in the ratio of 95:5 ($R_f=0.47$) as developers and iodine as indicator.

The deposited residue (A) was dissolved in acetone and the extract on chromatographic resolution over silica gel with benzene-chloroform (1:1) as eluent also yielded daphnoretin, m.p. 244-45°.

Acetylation of daphnoretin: Daphnoretin (50 mg) was refluxed with a mixture of acetic anhydride (5 ml) and pyridine (2 ml) on a water-bath for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 1 hr. and then poured to crushed ice with continuous stirring when a solid substance appeared. It was crystallised from chloroform:methanol (1:1), m.p. 233° (yield 25 mg), $R_f=0.80$ in chloroform-acetone (1:1).

Isolation of β -sitosterol: The petroleum ether extract was concentrated, cooled and chromatographed on silica gel. The benzene eluate on evaporation deposited a crystalline mass, m.p. 125°. It was recrystallised from methanol as colourless shining flakes, m.p. 136-37° (yield 0.018%), $(\alpha)_D = -35^\circ$, $R_f=0.53$ in $CHCl_3$ -MeOH (95:5).

Acetylation of β -sitosterol: The compound (50 mg) was treated with acetic anhydride (5 ml) and pyridine (2 ml). On usual processing, β -sitosterol acetate, m.p. 128-30° (MeOH) was obtained.

The authors express their sincere thanks to Professor R. Tschesche, University of Bonn, West Germany, for generous supply of an authentic sample of daphnoretin, to Dr. B. C. Das, Gif-sur-Yvette, France for mass spectrum. One of the authors (G.C.S.) is grateful to the Govt. of West Bengal for a research grant, to Dr. T. S. Bhattacharya, Principal, Hooghly Mohsin College for encouragement and to Professor (Mrs.) A. Chatterjee, University of Calcutta, for helpful discussions and laboratory facilities.

DEPARTMENT OF PURE CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE, CALCUTTA-9.

and

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
HOOGHLY MOHSIN COLLEGE,
CHINSURAH, HOOGHLY.

Received, July 25, 1968.